

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF COUNTING ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Esonova Malakhat Akilovna
Kokan State Pedagogical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8431268>

Annotation. This article explores the stages of development of counting activities of preschool children. Based on the conclusions drawn, proposals were developed.

Keywords: collection elements, equality, inequality, counting activities, counting activities stages, comparison, monetary units.

Results of counting, stages of development of counting activities. As a result of scientific examinations, it is determined that the progress of children's counting activities includes the following stages:

Stage 1. At this stage, children do business with a set of identical objects, separate them and, taking them from one place to another, build something. At this time, children divide the entire set into certain elements, and the sum of sound or actions begins to attach importance to the uniform repetition of elements.

Stage 2. At this stage, children begin to determine whether the elements interact in a one-value relationship, practically occupying the skill of comparing the elements of one set with the elements of the second set. As a result of practicing comparing elements of sets, they begin to notice equality or inequality between elements.

Stage 3. At this stage, children begin to master the number operation, counting the elements of the sets being compared and using the numbers appropriately. In the minds of children, a series of natural numbers is such a template of the concept of a set, with the help of which one begins to understand that it is possible to determine the elementary quantity of any set.

Stage 4. In doing so, children determine the correct and inverse relations between neighboring numbers, master the concept of number more deeply, and learn that the row of natural numbers is a certain system. Thus, in the process of children's counting activities, first of all, their perception of sets is composed, and then the concept of a system of numbers and number rows is composed. The fourth stage in the development of children's counting activities prepares them for a new activity, which makes it clear that children can work not only with specific sets, but also with numbers.

Thus, children move from perceived acceptance in the process of working directly with collections to conscious acceptance in a conscious clarity of thought.

In a large group, children are continued to be taught to count. Within 10, the qualification of using both quantity numbers and ordinal numbers is strengthened. The Child Is Called "How?" (about the quality, sign of the item: Green, large, round); "how much?" (about the quantity of the item); "Nechanchi?" (the position of the object between other items is determined by an ordinal number, e.g. a fifth), it is important to teach to understand questions in a differentiated (differential) case. In children, the formation of

connections between numbers is continued: each subsequent number is larger than the previous one, and the previous one is smaller than the next. Based on this, the perceptions of the relationships between adjacent numbers are assimilated: each next number is one more than the previous one, and each previous number is 1 smaller than the next. (5.6 to 1 small, 6.5 to 1 large, 6.7 to 1 small). After children have mastered that one number is 1 smaller (either larger) than the other, they are explained that if a small number is added 1, the next large number is formed, and if a large number is reduced by 1, the small, i.e. the previous number is formed. The connection between numbers and the relationship are all explained based on the comparison of groups of items. In the process of such exercises, the educator "how much was it?", "how much did they add (subtract)?", "how much has it been (how much)?", which uses questions such as

In a large group, it is necessary to provide children with knowledge that each number will receive a certain number of units within it. Representations of the composition of numbers within 5 consisting of units are also formulated in concrete examples.

Children are taught to analyze groups of items, by their signs, quality, and then tell the units of the number. For example, how many cubes are the tutor putting 4 cubes of different colors on the table?; how many in what color?, he asks. The final question directs the amount of items to be analyzed by their colors: "what color.how many from? - 1 Red, 1 Blue, 1 yellow, 1 green". - "Hammasichi?"- "All 4 cubes" - " so 4 is 1, 1, 1 and 1. After that, again, children are asked to say the units of the number, and then the number itself (1,1,1 and 1 are 4).

When teaching preschool children, it is necessary to use their various knowledge of items, their differentiation or integration into groups, generalizations skills in particular symptoms. For example, there are 5 toys in total. "How much?"-"1 rabbit, 1 bear, 1 bear, 1 doll, 1 Fox".- "So 5 is 1, 1, 1, 1, and 1". All in the child

it is from this that the skill is formed to see the quantity and say it, to say the units of the number (any unit that constructs the number), to combine them and say them with a number.

When studying the composition of a number consisting of units, it is necessary to use children's knowledge of geometric shapes, knowledge of the relationships of objects in terms of their magnitudes, and their relative magnitudes, which they can say. For example, when analyzing the composition of the number 3 consisting of one, it is possible to take geometric shapes: Triangle, Circle, Square; analysis of the composition of the number 5 consisting of one can take pieces of paper of different lengths and colors for qnlish. One of these pieces is yellow - shortest, one is blue - slightly longer, one is green - even longer, one is white - 2 is less long, one is red - longest, and jamn 5 is 1, 1, 1, 1, and 1.

Children need to consolidate the knowledge gained with the help of various tasks. For example, the tutor shows a number card and offers the children to jsyize the items so that the number of units is invisible. Or it shows a 3-round, numbered card, while the children put a circle, a triangle and a square. Children can be asked why they counted 3 shapes apart, which shapes he separated (1 Circle, 1 triangle, 1 square), how many units there were in 3 numbers. Thus, the educator introduces children to the generation of natural numbers: depending on whether the number is gained or reduced by one unit, a large or small number is formed.

In a large group, the qualification of using ordinal numbers in children is continued rnojlantnrish. Even at this age, the child often replaces the ordinal value of the number with the quantitative value. Therefore, it is necessary to reveal to children the essence of the ordinal number, to show that the quantitative number does not always fall with the ordinal number, and to show that the ordinal number always expresses a certain amount of items. How much is the order "to" children until the introduction of the number? when answering the question "is it necessary not only to count from left to right, but also to indicate that it is possible to count both from right to left and from the middle, and not from a row, but from any items placed differently. If the count (remembering that the count began with the item and which was counted) is taken correctly, the result will always be the same.

The child is listed in the order number "nechanchi?" should master the fact that the items are always arranged in rows when the question is asked to be answered. Usually, the count is from left to right (it is also possible to count from right to left, but the child must know in what order the count is carried out).

Children learn that the orientation of the number is important in determining the order of the item between other items. The educator always asks "how much?" by saying how many of the items listed in the question were all, "which?" ("number nechanchi?") reminds and emphasizes the question that one item must be answered by knowing its position between the other items, and must be counted as first, second, third.

The children were asked "which?", "nechanchi?" it is advisable to use the skills of comparing them according to the size and color of the items, in order to understand the questions and practice the difference. For example, they are instructed to find out how much the colored piece of paper is in total; what color is the first piece above; which piece is the fifth, the green piece is the nechanchi on account, and the black piece is the nechanchi on account. In such assignments, geometric shapes—a large triangle, a circle, a triangle, a rectangle, a large triangle of the same color, but of different sizes, a large circle, large rectangles can be used. He ("howchanchi on the big circle count?, which form is the fourth? Nechanchi on a large rectangular number?" Say the next form. How is he? What is the sixth form called?». "Which?" the qualification of understanding the question is also strengthened in exercises to determine knowledge about the week. For example, what is the first day of the week of the educator?, how is the third day of the week called, How is the day of the week Thursday? etc.k. questions should be expressed differently. This allows both concentration of attention and a more thorough assimilation of knowledge. Game methods are also effective.

The Chunonchi, the teacher speaks, and he follows his speech with a display on a flannelegraph. Tell me what kind of animals are in the meadow. Animals must be transferred to the other shore. Because the bridge is narrow, they follow each other in a row. See carefully bnlan, what is going on first? What's going on second? What is going after the cow? ... What is going before Aries? What is going on at the end? How is the lamb on account? How many animals are crossing the bridge in total? A large group of preschool-age children will continue to be taught to say equalities using expressions such as two, five, nine, of different located items of different sizes.

It is advisable to give preliminary information in exercises performed with didactic dispensing materials. The child can be offered to separate 4 triangles and arrange them in rows; divide so many circles and place them under triangles; place an equal number of

squares under circles under them, and re-count the number of triangles, dopras, squares. Finally, this question should also be asked, "how many geometric shapes are in each row?». This question can be allowed to be answered in different ways: a compact answer – "out of four"; the complete answer is: "four geometric shapes" or "four geometric shapes are placed in each row".

References:

1. Makhamatalikizi, A. N. (2021). Necessity and Problems of Typological Study of Onomatopoeia. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 101-102.
2. Aliboeva, N. (2022). The expression of comparative analysis. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 93-95.
3. Abdukakhhorovna, J. M. (2021). Scientific Views on the Development of the Anthropocentric Paradigm in Linguistics. *JournalNX*, 7(07), 20-21.
4. Abdukahhorovna, J. M. (2021). History of the study of introductions and entries in russian linguistics. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(1), 238-240.
5. Abdukakhhorovna, J. M. (2020, June). THE SYSTEM OF PHONETIC GAMES IN THE TEACHING OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 70-71).
6. Жураева, М. А. (2016). ВНЕКЛАСНАЯ РАБОТА В СИСТЕМЕ НЕПРЕРЫВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ (ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ КВН). *Вестник современной науки*, (2-2), 94-96.
7. Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES OF THE WORDS OF MASTERING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE UZBEK LITERARY LANGUAGE. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 110-112.
8. Soliev, O. (2022). GENERAL CONCEPTS ABOUT EDUCATIONAL LAWS AND METHODS OF EFFECTIVE USING THEM IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(4), 448-452.
9. Ахмедова, Р. М., & Адиллов, Ф. А. (2016). Подготовка специалистов в отрасли ремесленного производства в 20-х годах XX века. *Ученый XXI века*, (5-4 (18)), 62-64.
10. Ахмедова, Р. (2020). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ДАСТЛАБКИ ШИФО МАСКАНЛАРИНИНГ ВУЖУДГА КЕЛИШИ (ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ МИСОЛИДА). *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ*, (SI-1№ 1).
11. Mukimovna, A. R. (2020, December). History of children's sanatorium resorts in Uzbekistan (1930-1953). In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 311-314).
12. BURIYEV, S., MAXKAMOVA, D., & SHERIMBETOV, V. (2020). Ekologiya va atrof muhit muhofazasi. O'quv qo'llanma. T-innovatsiya ziyo.
13. Ахмедова, Р. М. (2022). From the history of the socio-material situation of the population of Uzbekistan (on the example of 1920-1940). *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 243-247.
14. Ahmedova, R., & Muxtorova, M. (2023). FARG'ONA VODIYSIDAGI SHIFO MASKANLARINING VUJUDGA KELISHI TARIXIDAN ("CHORTOQ" SIHATGOXI MISOLIDA). *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).
15. Ahmedova, R., & Muxtorova, M. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON SANATORIY-KURORTLARI DAVOLASH ISHLARIDAGI AYRIM MUAMMOLAR TARIXI. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).

- 16.Ahmedova, R., & Shokirova, A. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF REFORMS IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS LEGAL FRAMEWORK OVER THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 1112-1116.
- 17.Mukimovna, A. R., Asqarovna, Q. S., & Sodiqovich, K. Q. (2022). HISTORY OF SOME PROBLEMS IN TREATMENT WORKS OF SANATORIUMS AND SPAS OF UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
- 18.Abdukakhhorovna, Z. M. (2022). Lexical Polysemy of the Russian Language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 77-81.
- 19.Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE-SPEECH COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(02), 8-11.
- 20.Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). Working On Words With An Untested Unstressed Vowel At The Root Of A Word In Elementary School. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 145-149.
- 21.Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). PRIORITIES OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 113-119.
- 22.Soliyev, O. (2022). PEDAGOGIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA ILMIY-TADQIQOT METODLARIDAN FOYDALANISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 38-42.
- 23.Алибаева, Н. М. (2017). Бадий матнларда эмоционал гаплар. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 2-3.
- 24.Isoqjonova, D., & Aliboyeva, N. (2020). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA INTENSIVLIK SEMANTIKASINI IFODALOVCHI XARAKAT FE'LLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 363-366).
- 25.қизи Алибоева, Н. М., & Хошимов, Д. (2022). Тақлидий сўзларни типологик ўрганиш муаммолари. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 380-382.
- 26.Madumarov, T., & Ogli, G. O. R. (2023). FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM). *Educational sacrifices*, 02-05.

